

Best Practices in Managing Customers Complaints in Selected Quick Service Restaurants in Dasmariñas City

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6772549>

Published Date: 28-June-2022

Abstract: This research was carried out to find out the best practices for dealing with customer complaints in Dasmariñas City's quick-service restaurants. The researchers of this study used the Purposive Sampling Technique to perform a descriptive survey among twenty QSR customers and ten QSR managers to learn about their insights founded on their own customer complaint experiences. Through data gathering, this study was able to find out that the demographic profile of customers affects the way they address their concerns to a QSR manager. Conversely, the demographic profile of the QSR managers affects the way they address the concerns of their customers. Most especially, their experiences from their educational attainments, given that the majority reached the college level, up to their working attainments where the majority are employees, make up the behaviors they have in a QSR. This study obtained information such as recommendations from all respondents about the best practices in managing customer complaints in QSRs, which whoever needs to know, may utilize for their own good such as students, researchers, and businesses.

Keywords: customer complaint management, customer satisfaction, food industry, quick service restaurant, QSR.

I. INTRODUCTION

Managing customer complaints is not a skill that is practised by Quick Service Restaurant (QSR) waiters or waitresses, the manager, the chef, nor in small or big restaurants only. Instead, it is a necessary skill for all QSR employees in line with the industry that they are in, where the customers are the sales and sustainability leaders, according to Melissa Rose (2021).

Oftentimes, handling a single customer concern can make or break an employee, or even the QSR's success, as the result of an event could either turn a customer into a loyal one or drive them away. Also, it is not only a single customer that complaints come with— there is always a possibility that the customer will share their experience with others, whether it was a good or bad experience. Hence, the image of a QSR can be positively or negatively affected— may it be on the service quality, food quality, facilities, or the environment/ambience.

Nonetheless, people are all different from one another, thus, a single method of attending to their concerns will never be enough. So, to help ease the said instance, this study was carried out to acquire fresh valuable ideas from the customer and managerial end. Data like the basis of customer satisfaction to a complaint occurrence are just a few details gained from this study. Additionally, the complaint management methods of several managers were found to be reliant on their professional skills, knowledge of the product and QSR where they work, as well as their professional background. These specifics could be used by the target beneficiaries of this study including Bachelor of Science in Hotel Restaurant Management students, managers, as well as existing and future businesses.

II. METHODOLOGY

This chapter focus on the discussion of the Research design and procedures on how the researchers finding a solution in order to answer systematically the specific problems in this research. Specifically, the Research methods and the study of the participant's experience and opinions will be explained in this chapter.

Research Design

The study will employ qualitative type of research. The use of qualitative type of research in any study is necessary since there are no date to be manipulated. This research method was use since the researchers will focus to the opinions and experiences of the participants to achieve the purpose of the study. Descriptive research design allows the study to describe the best practices in managing customer complaints in Selected Quick Service Restaurant in Dasmariñas Cavite.

Participants of the Study

The Study will use Purposive Sampling as the sampling technique. The respondents of the study will be a total of 10 managers from two different fast-food restaurant inside the mall and 10 customers on each fast food restaurant. For the total of 10 managers and 20 customers that will enough provide a result from material used in research method. Customer survey needs to address the economic sustainability of the food establishments while Managers has the most responsible for taking up a solution from every situation that the customer complaints. Both have a vital role for the result of the study.

Research Instrument

The instrumentation that was used in the study is interviews in forms of online surveys.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher will use survey questionnaire in data gathering. The researcher will be handed out the survey in an online manner using the google forms. After handling out the questionnaire, it will be collected by the researcher from the respondents for the researcher listed their answers for further statistical analysis. The questionnaire will be validated by the adviser. The study will also use face validity to validate the survey questionnaire by using the respondents to validate if the survey questionnaire could answer the intended question on the best practices in managing customer complaints in selected fast food restaurant. This will serve as the test run in proceeding with the real survey test that was done. The data that the research retrieved will be treated with utmost confidentiality.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The researchers were able to meet the expected number of participants with a Purposive Sampling technique. Two separate questionnaires were prepared for ten (10) managers and twenty (20) customers, and the interview was conducted through an online survey using Google forms. The data obtained in both surveys were divided into two parts, namely the demographic profile made up of five characteristic queries, and the six (6) interview answers of the respondents.

A. Results

Figures 1.1 –1.5 (See appendices) show the demographic profile of the managers, who vary in age from 20 to 50 years old, with around seven of them being female, with earnings ranging from Php 6,000 to Php 20,000, educational attainment varying from high school to college degree, and are all employees.

Figures 2.1 - 2.5 (See appendices) are the demographic profile of the customers whose ages range from 15 to 30 years old, eleven are female, the incomes range from Php 2,000 to Php 20,000, whose educational attainments are within the scope of high school graduate and college undergraduate, and occupation varies from the unemployed, self-employed, student, and an employee.

Table 1. (See appendices) The table summarizes the answers of ten managers to the six questions prepared by the researchers.

Table 2. (See appendices) The table represents the answers of twenty (20) customers to the six (6) questions formulated by the researchers.

B. Discussion

The data presented in Figures 1.1 - 1.5 contains the demographic profile of the ten (10) manager respondents where most ages rely on in 20 to 50 years old, while the answers to the interview are presented in Table 1. As shown, the approach to addressing customer concerns is mostly about their listening skill, giving out coupons, as well as the Listen, Apologize, Solve, Thank (LAST) customer service acronym. Fundamentally, these management tips are already proven to be effective, as per the experience of the interviewed respondents, just like how these kinds of strategies were researched and mentioned in the literature review portion of this study.

Likewise, Figures 2.1 - 2.5 show the demographic profile of the twenty (20) respondents whose occupations vary from high school graduates up to employees. Theoretically, such data proves the hypothesis made by the researchers, which says that there is a significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and the customer service management. Information including the effectiveness and satisfaction of the respondents with the approaches of the managers were demonstrated by 18 out of 20 respondents who assured that they will purchase again even after a complaint scenario due to the proper addressing of the managers they have encountered.

Lastly, both customers and managers gave their recommendations to the involved parties, for the betterment of the food industry. Such includes having long patience, a listening ear, and to keep the concern between the managers themselves and the customers concerned.

IV. CONCLUSION

To conclude, the researchers were able to answer the five (5) statements of the problem mentioned in the introduction of the study, as well as prove the hypothesis stated. With the help of thirty (30) respondents, the involvement of the customers and managers in customer complaint management was proven to be related. The majority of the complaints were also found, which include the service and food quality, which the addressing was provided by a Quick Service Restaurant manager. According to the customers as well, the majority of the concerns were properly tackled, although one (1) out of twenty (20) respondents have decided to never come back to a QRS where they have experienced an issue. On the flip side, tips like focusing on their task, putting the customers first, and assuring the success of addressing a customer complaint were given by the manager respondents. Fairly enough, most of the customer complaints that they have managed were concluded to be a success, according to a total of ten (10) out of ten (10) respondents. Finally, all data and information obtained from this study can be used by all of its beneficiaries in the said industry.

V. APPENDIX

Fig. 1.1 Demographic Profile of the Managers

Fig. 1.2. Gender of the Managers

Fig. 1.3. Income of the Managers

Fig. 1.4. Educational Attainment of the Managers

Fig. 1.5. Occupation of the Managers

Fig. 2.1. Age of the Customers

Fig. 2.2 Gender of the Customers

Figure 2.3. Income of the Customers

Figure 2.4. Educational Attainment

Figure 2.5. Occupation of the Customers

TABLE I. Responses of the Managers

Response No.	How do you act on complains?	What are the plans you implement during the complains?	What service do you offer the most to avoid complains?	What can you offer to the customer after the complaints scenario?	Was your complaints most resolve? Why?	What recommendations you want to share about handling customer complains?
1	Listen first to complainant and pacify them by correcting what they are complaining	Listen first to complainant and pacify them by correcting what they are complaining	Satisfactory service	Correcting the service or product they complain	Yes	Be calm, listen to them first, and satisfy them.
2	It depends about the complaint. First you need to apologize on what happened.	We need to settle this complaint as soon as possible	Nothing. Do the standard procedure to avoid complains	Its depend on the situation. If the complaint is product quality. You may replace her/him order to give satisfaction on the customers.	I immediately called the complainant and apologized for what happened.	Sincerely apologized to the customer.
3	Polite listen to them	apologize and give them extra credits	making sure that shift is smooth and manageable	replacement, extra	yes, because we listen to them first and apologize and give them replacement or extra for the product	Politely listen, apologize and satisfy them with extra
4	Stay calm and listen to their concern.	Know the root cause and resolved the issue.	Exceptional service.	Assurance. Making sure that we will take corrective actions regarding that matter to avoid happening again.	Yes. Attend immediately to their concern.	When it comes to handling customer complains, you need to make sure that the customer will be satisfied with the action you have provided to resolve the issue.
5	Being professional and handle to resolve the complains	Using LAST means listen, apologize, satisfied and of course say thank you to the customer	Faster service and good quality of products	Replaced the product that he/her complaint and apologize	Yes, because we handle it proper, for example we have lacking on delivery we deliver it as soon as possible to the customers	Always say please and thank you
6	Worries	First listen to the customer and accommodate properly, and give the solutions	Good service	Please visit and i promise did not happen again	Manny	Be very patience and listen carefully to the customer
7	P-olitely L-	To correct	Customer	We offer products	Yes, we	The win back

	isten E-xpress, A-pology, S-atisfy with extras	immediately of a certain complaint or to have action taken.	Service	that can complement to his /her inconvenience	usually listen first to the customer and investigate what are the roots cause of the complaints	situations every complaint you must have a goal to return back your customer to your restaurant.
8	Listen on what customer's complaint, be polite and put yourself on customer's seat.	N/A	In food industry like restaurant and fast food , most of the times they complaints about of too long of waiting orders , wrong orders , non-available product, not satisfaction food served. Therefore, to prevent those situations, we need to spend focus for all the whole service time , a fast service and accuracy of food orders	We offer that it will not happened again and hoping that they will come again.	N/A	N/A
9	Listen to the concern of customer	I promise that it will never happen again	I will give the very best to avoid complaints	The best thing I offer to the customer is to replace there order a newly cook product and some small freebies	About product quality, the food had insect I quickly apologize to the customer and replace the food, and the customer is satisfied about what I'm doing with their complain.	Listen to the customer complain and apologize for what happen and always thank the customer for the concern so that you can improve your service
10	First, I will give way the customer to speak of what their minds and side. Next will listen carefully and will make a respond politely like making them will going to listen and calm. And will apologize and asking for kindness for changing a product ordered into a new fresh meal he/she ordered.	A plan that will make them stay to our store even the scene happened and will the best to convince the customers.	An energetic and welcoming voice when they enter the store to make them feels that they are special customer of the store.	How about a gift check or a product meal we are serving.	Yes, because I always take up on my mind that no matter what we should love and appreciate customers. And the consistency of me for them.	Always be polite in personal especially when facing customer.

TABLE II. Responses of the Customers

Response No.	How managers approach when you complains?	How do you appreciate their actions to value your complaints?	What can you say about their service offer?	Will you purchase again even after the complaint's experience? Why?	Did you satisfy to their actions? Why?	What recommendations you want to share to the managers in handling customer complaints?
1	They greet first and asking me the problem then they politely listen and express apology.	When they give action for the complaints and assurance that it will never happen again.	They have good service and people that serves great service.	Yes, because I believe we're not perfect we should understand that this kind of issue can happen which is not expected.	Yes, because they assured it never happen again and they gave an satisfy with extra.	Maintain the practices that implemented when handling customer complaints because it is effective to assure that customer is satisfy for the solution they made.
2	They listen to my complaint first and after hearing my complaint they offer a genuine apology.	They apologize and reiterate my understanding of the issue.	What can I say about their service is great, because they are well trained when it comes to handling complaints and they make people welcome.	Yes, I will purchase again, because they showed me how great their service is and how much they valued their customers.	Yes, I am, because they fixed right away my complaint and reassured that they will take care more to prevent those emergencies that caused a complain.	Be calm always when they talk to the complainants, show that you are listening to what they are complaining and give a proper action that you would not offend the customers.
3	They face and explain my complaint	When they gave effort to explain the complaints	They have a great service	Yes, because they meet my satisfaction	Yes, because they meet my satisfaction after my complaint	Give an extra effort even it is small complaints.
4	They talk to me with respect and ask me about my complaint with their calm voice.	giving customers feedback	Very accommodating	Yes, valuing their service for me is okay. Complaints can be corrected.	Yes, it's a good action to take for their customer to repeat business with them	Ask directly what customers recommendation for service improvements.
5	They let me talk about my complaint, then they apologize and make an action to solve my complaint.	Appreciated	Satisfy	Yes, its their service	Yes, provide assurance	For my recommendation, I would suggest that always show to the customer that you are willing to fix their complaints. Show your concern face to them and also don't forget to ask them if they are good for the solutions, you had made
6	With respect and discipline	Being patient and trying to solve the problem.	Good service	Yes, because I know history and problem	Yes, because there's easy to solve the problems.	Always remember customers is always right.
7	They are very accommodating	Highly appreciated because I feel like they are really dedicated to do	Approachable	Yes, if the manager handled my complain and fix it	yes, because they are approachable	please hold your temper we only need your answers to our questions.

		their job.				
8	They are being polite and calm when asking the problem.	Much appreciated because they manage and take actions or solutions and acknowledge my complain	Its good	Yes, probably if they manage and handle well the complain	Yes, because they take actions and handle it well.	Hear the customers complain and think how to handle it well.
9	Understanding and Calm	I'll say thank you and comeback again	Its fast and accurate	Yes, because it can be a onetime mistake	Yes, because they take action	Be more patient
10	Some are nice and some are rude a little bit.	Actually it's really nice if they can accommodate if I have some complain..		No because there is a bad experience already.	Sometimes.	Just give their best to explain to guest what the problem is and be nice to the guest.
11	They politely with sincerity.	If they are gives take action from my complaint and I thankful for that.	The service is good and the food is yummy.	Yes, because I had food that I wanted to eat again.	Yes. Because the gave action for my complaint	Just keep employee well trained about handling customer. Always keep the practices on handling customer with politely.
12	They Calmly approaches me and explain things.	By thanking them	Good service	Yes, because they already fixed what i have been complaint	Yes, because they are fast to respond	Always calm.
13	Nice and	When they are approaching in a proper way And saying sorry for what have done. And giving assurance that next time it wouldn't happen again.	Very well	Yes, why not? Because some mistakes never happen again. Because of action plans.	Yes. Because of respecting of my complain.	Have some space when listening to the customer complaints, don't bother any customers and it can be good if you have to listen to each other's side.
14	please	Very happy, especially when they accommodate me and fixed right away about my complaint.	Nothing	Yes	Yes	nothing
15	Nothing	Learnings and Improvement	Don't know	Yes, because I have to another skills	Independent	For more grow up as a person
16	Very humble and they know how deal regarding to my complaint.	I will still purchase their products	They are polite and calm	Yes, because the products are nice.	Yes, they are calm and well-communicate	
17	Nice and clear	Very well appreciated	Great	Yes, but I'm going to give myself a week to get back to their restaurant or store for them to be able to have enough time to serve their customers	Yes. Because it is not easy to handle some customer complains. In a restaurant this is the very	You should not just give the wants of your customers but also their needs because not all customers have a flexible mind to be

				after my complain.	crucial thing they've ever experience.	able to understand everything. Talk to them politely and understand the situation first before making decisions.
18	Polite and asking what the complain about	I thank them for the assistance	It depends on the situation, but most of the time I am satisfy.	Yes of course.	Yes of course.	Be polite and be humble
19	None because I'm the manager	By respecting them	It's good	Yes, because it's a one mistake	Yes, because it's a one mistake	As a manager I recommend being obedient and kind to their customer
20	They usually ask me to tell the details of my complaint before properly addressing it.	I always give thanks and respond to whatever they are saying.	Depends on the situation.	It depends. Usually, if I'm after the foods offered, then it's highly likely that I'll purchase again. But if everything, including the food and the customer service failed, then I wouldn't purchase again.	Yes, if my concern was addressed.	I would recommend to managers to always be calm even if the customers are rude, because such are hard to dodge. But it would be best to address their concerns whether they are asking for one or not, since it's important for them to know the root of their complaints-- for both the customer and the restaurant's sake.

VI. RECOMMENDATION

This research paper meets the solutions of the statement of the problem were able to find and answered by the survey used. This study will benefit every quick service restaurant Dasmariñas Cavite in able to apply the best practices in managing customer complaints.

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